

Development of a culture on Research Data Management: experiences from the international RDMS-LatAm Project

Extended Summary

Research Data Management is based on the so-called “FAIR Principles” of data, whose fundamental objective is to make the latter freely findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, thus promoting the adoption of these principles by institutions as standards of good practices. Universities, in their role as teaching and research centers, must embrace such principles in order to develop science of higher quality, accessibility, visibility and impact.

The concepts of Research Data Management (RDM), Open Data (OD) and Open Science (OS) are relatively new around the world. In Latin America and the Caribbean they have been introduced by organizations such as the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC), the Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR) and the Federated Network of Institutional Repositories of Scientific Publications of Latin America (La Reference). In 2020 UNESCO made a “Recommendation on Open Science”, with regional offices (e.g. Havana) as implementers in the Latin American and Caribbean region. Different countries, including Peru, have developed legislation on open access and repositories.

Methodology

Cross-sectional descriptive research, while the characteristics and results achieved by the project are reviewed: “Development of a research data management strategy in Higher Education and Research Institutes in a Latin American context” (RDMS-LatAm), in its first year of development in the 4 participating Latin American universities: Universidad Central “Marta Abreu” de Las Villas (UCLV) and Universidad de Cienfuegos “Carlos Rafael Rodríguez” (Cuba), Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos (Peru), Universidad Católica Boliviana San Pablo. Documentary analysis was used as a research method, to investigate and interpret, as well as review different existing documentary sources to understand the RDM phenomenon.

Results

So far, the actions of RDMS-LatAm have allowed the development of 4 lines of work: 1-Diagnosis on RDM practices, 2-Policies for the RDM development, 3-Training of teachers, researchers, librarians and managers in relation to RDM, as well as such as the 4-Establishment of collaborative networks.

1-Diagnosis on RDM practices

A diagnosis was carried out on a representative sample of decision makers, professors and researchers from the four universities, with the aim of identify RDM practices in these institutions. As result, the following difficulties were identified: Lack of policies and standards for RDM, Inefficient and ineffective management of Research Data that leads to its loss, Lack of infrastructure that allows adequate RDM, Need to develop and validate an instrument to diagnose RDM practices more adapted to the Latin American environment.

A new questionnaire was developed and validated to diagnose RDM practices. It maintained the 5 dimensions analyzed by the questionnaire initially designed and applied; modifications were made to several questions, as well as the elimination and addition of new ones. Validation was carried out using specialist’s criteria, Alpha Cronbach’s coefficient and a pilot test applied to a sample of professors, researchers and decision makers from a stakeholder university of RDMS-LatAm in Cuba.

2-Policies for the RDM development

After an analysis of experiences on the continent on OC practices and especially on the management of research data, the four member institutions have developed policy proposals for RDM. They are being analyzed by administrative directives for approval and implementation. The policy proposals have been structured with the following sections: Introduction, Definitions, Scope, Purpose, FAIR Principles of Research Data, Research Data Management Plans Data Metadata and Documentation, Roles and Responsibilities, Ownership and Rights of Ownership Author on Research Data, Documents and Related Regulations

3-Training of teachers, researchers, librarians and managers regarding RDM.

During the first year of work, 10 members of the project (5 CUB, 3 PER and 2 BOL) received training on RDM with specialists from 3 universities in Belgium, the latter with palpable results in this regard within the consortium of Flemish universities.

Research Data Management was included in the undergraduate degree of Information Sciences and in the postgraduate course as a master's program "Information and Knowledge for Development" in the UCLV, in the latter, in addition to the students, also they included librarians from said institution. The Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos also included RDM as part of the Doctoral training in the Health Sciences program.

In each of the participating Latin American institutions, leading researchers were selected, who have been trained through online workshops on topics related to RDM such as: Development of policies for RDM, Organization of Research Data, Management Plans of the Research Data, Data Storage and on the Protection of Research Data.

4-Establishment of collaboration networks

In addition to the relationships developed between the 5 member universities of the project, collaborations have been established with other institutions interested in the results of RDMS-LatAm: National Council of Science, Technology and Technological Innovation (Peru), University of Medical Sciences of Villa Clara, Science Division of the Ministry of Science, Technology and Environment (Cuba), Science Division of the Ministry of Higher Education (Cuba), Institute of Scientific and Technical Documentation and Information (Cuba), University of Pinar del Rio "Hermanos Sainz" (Cuba), University of Camagüey "Ignacio Agramonte" (Cuba), National Institute of Sports and Recreation (Cuba), Research, Science and Technology Division of the Bolivian University System.

Conclusions

Research Data Management has been established as one of the pillars for the development of Open Science, the sustainability, reproducibility and verifiability of research activity in general. The preservation and socialization of DI drives the genesis of new projects and scientific collaboration.

RDMS-LatAm constitutes the first initiative of its kind in Cuba, Bolivia and Peru, contributing to the development of a culture about RDM among the scientific community of these nations.